

Selection of the model functions for calculations of high-overtone intensities in the vibrational-rotational spectra of diatomic molecules

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The initial information on the molecular functions necessary for calculations of spectra is always of discrete nature, being either quantum-chemical calculations or experimental data. Selection of the model functions built on this information and then used to calculate the intensities of the fundamental transitions and low overtones is not restricted by any conditions, yet these same functions can result in errors when used for the high-overtone transitions. In particular, the errors are found in calculations for OH, PN, YO, CaO, PS, NS, SH, PH, and NO. We analyze the sources of the errors and give recommendations of how to avoid them. The molecular functions should be chosen such that the Normal Intensity Distribution Law is fulfilled. In order to increase the accuracy of the calculations, it is also desirable that their analytical properties in the complex plane be as close as possible to those of the real functions.

Keywords: NIDL, repulsive branch, analytical functions, branch points, damped coordinate, saturation of the intensities

Introduction

The main feature of the overtone transitions is very rapid decrease of their intensities with increasing the overtone number – the intensity drops by 1-2 orders of magnitude when going to the next overtone so that quadruple precision is required for very high overtones [1]. Quantitatively, this is described by the so-called Normal Intensity Distribution Law (NIDL) according to which logarithm of intensity is linear function of square root of the upper-state energy, E_v , in units of vibrational quantum ω [2] (see also review [3] and references therein). Exceptions are the anomalies, i.e. isolated lines, whose intensities are much lower than those of the NIDL, which is a consequence of a specific interference effect [3,4]. The NIDL is fulfilled for all diatomic molecules as well as for quasidiatomic local vibrations in polyatomic molecules, which was confirmed by experimental and theoretical data [2,5-7]. The physical origin of the NIDL is described in detail in Refs. [3,8,9], where it is shown to be intimately associated with the behavior of the molecular potential in the region of strong repulsion. The NIDL is a powerful tool to analyze the calculated intensities of the overtone transitions.

To calculate the intensities of dipole transitions, one needs to know the potential energy, $U(r)$, and the electric dipole moment, $d(r)$, of the molecule as functions of the interatomic separation, r . In the case of transitions with small change of the vibrational quantum number, v , typically $\Delta v \leq 2$, the form of these functions has no effect on the results, yet this is not true for higher transitions. In particular, based on the intensity calculations for the $v \leftarrow 0$ transitions in SiO, CS, CO, and LiCl, it was shown that the use of non-analytic functions with discontinuities in derivatives, e.g. splines, lead to non-physical saturation of the intensities at $v \geq 5$ for SiO [10], $v \geq 7$ for CS [1,11], CO and LiCl [10]. Therefore, contemporary calculations use only the analytical functions [12], however the problem nevertheless persists because, as we will see, some additional restrictions are required.

Further investigations showed that the model functions should possess special properties of analyticity in the complex plane similar to those of the true molecular functions [13], and a method was proposed permitting to establish the degree of such a similarity quantitatively [9,13]. It is based on the obvious requirement that the results of the calculations be relatively insensitive to the choice of the forms of the dipole-moment function (DMF) having formally different analytical properties. In Ref. [9], an example of similar intensities for CO calculated with the irregular DMF having branch points and with a rational function was given. In such a case, it can be expected that the remaining differences provide for estimates of the calculation accuracy.

In this paper, using the NIDL, we analyze the calculated data for several diatomic molecules from the international databases ExoMol [14] and HITEMP [15] and propose methods to improve the calculation accuracy. Significant breakdowns of the NIDL are treated as errors due to incorrect choice of the DMF or the potential energy function, the justification is given in **Discussion**. The methods to increase the calculation accuracy are considered in **Conclusions**.

Intensity saturation due to non-analyticity of DMF

The figures below show the intensities of transitions $v', J' \leftarrow v'', J''$ from the lower state $v'' = 0, E'' = 0$ (except for Fig. 7 for SH), $J'' = 0, 0.5, 1, \text{ or } 1.5$ to the upper state $v' = v \geq 1, J' = J'' + 1$. To draw the NIDL straight line, the points starting from the first overtone $v = 2$ excluding the anomalies are used.

Fig. 1. The calculated Einstein A coefficient, A_{v0} (in s^{-1}), for vibrational-rotational transitions in the ground electronic state, $X^2\Pi$, of hydroxyl radical, data of Ref. [16] taken from the ExoMol database (<https://www.exomol.com/>). $J'' = 0.5$, $v = 1-13$. The NIDL line is drawn through points $v = 2-8$, $\omega = 3738.465 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [16]; point $v = 9$ is possibly the anomaly.

In Fig. 1, data of Brooke *et al.* [16] for hydroxyl radical are given. The points decline from the NIDL linear dependence at $v \geq 9$ because of spline implementation.

Shown in Fig. 2 are data of Yorke *et al.* [17] for phosphorus nitride. Deviations from the linear NIDL due to the use of splines occur at $v \geq 6$. Wrong data at $v \geq 6$ were not included in ExoMol.

Fig. 2. The Einstein coefficients for transitions in state $X^1\Sigma^+$ of phosphorus nitride from Ref. [17]. $J'' = 0$, $v = 1-66$. The NIDL line is drawn through points $v = 2-5$, points $v \geq 6$ are wrong.

A similar situation takes place for yttrium oxide (Fig. 3) and calcium oxide (Fig. 4). Saturation due to splines was also observed for carbon monosulphide (CS), see Fig. 3 in our paper [1] and Fig. 4 in Ref. [11]. In Ref. [11], a piece-wise dipole moment with discontinuities in

derivatives at $r = 1$ и 3.4 \AA was proposed, but it should also result in strong deviations from the NIDL.

Fig. 3. The Einstein coefficients for transitions in state $X^2\Sigma^+$ of yttrium oxide from Ref. [18]. $J''=0.5$. Point $v = 4$ is the anomaly. The NIDL line is drawn through points $v = 2,3,5,6$. $\omega = 861.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [18]. Points $v = 7-17$ are wrong.

Fig. 4. The Einstein coefficients for transitions in state $X^1\Sigma^+$ of calcium oxide from Ref. [19]. $J''=0$. Point $v = 4$ is the anomaly. The NIDL line is drawn through points $v = 2,3,5,6$. $\omega = 733.4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [20]. Points $v = 7-12$ are wrong.

Intensity saturation due to rapid DMF variations in the complex plane

Based on our arguments about the necessity of using analytical functions, the authors of Ref. [12] proposed an analytical model DMF in the form of polynomial in the so-called damped coordinate,

Fig. 5. The Einstein coefficients for transitions in state $X^2\Pi$ of phosphorus monosulphide from Ref. [12]. $J'' = 0.5$, $v = 1-81$. The NIDL line is drawn through points $v = 2-9$. Points $v = 13$ and 19 are possibly the anomalies. Points $v > 20$ are wrong.

$$z = (r - r_{\text{ref}}) \exp \left[-\beta_2 (r - r_{\text{ref}})^2 - \beta_4 (r - r_{\text{ref}})^4 \right], \quad (1)$$

where r_{ref} is a fixed parameter close to the equilibrium bond length, r_e , and β_2, β_4 are adjustable parameters. However, the polynomial in z variable does not meet the requirement that the DMF did not change too fast in the complex plane of r [9]; in fact, it is exponentially increasing and oscillating. Unfortunately there is no way to learn whether there is a NIDL breakdown in Fig. 5 for phosphorus monosulphide because the saturation at $v > 15$ is caused by the use of double precision in numerical procedures. We remind that the double precision in carbon monoxide (CO) caused the saturation at $v > 20$ [21] with similar values of A . The same situation takes place for nitrogen monosulfide (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. The Einstein coefficients for transitions in state $X^2\Pi$ of nitrogen sulphide from Ref. [22]. $J'' = 0.5$, $v = 1-36$. The NIDL line is drawn through points $v = 3-9$. Points 2 and 11 are possibly the anomalies. Points $v > 12$ are wrong.

Let us discuss in more detail the results for thio(mercapto) radical (Fig. 7) from Yurchenko *et al.* [22] and Gorman *et al.* [23]. The first paper considers transitions in the isolated ground electronic state X whereas excited states A and B as well as the *ab initio* spin-orbit interactions X-X, X-A, and X-B were added in the second one. Despite the energy minimum of state A is reached at level $v = 25$ of state X, the second paper notes an appreciable contribution of state A to the calculated absorption spectra at energies higher than 10000 cm^{-1} corresponding to level $v = 5$ of state X. Therefore the observed intensity **increase** in the interval of $v = 9-12$ could be associated with a contribution of state A. In fact, as shown by comparison of the data from these two works in Fig. 7 (circles and crosses), the contribution of state A in the range of $v = 1-14$ is relatively small and is in no way responsible for the incorrect behavior, i.e. the increase of the intensities above the anomaly assumed at $v = 8$. As an alternative explanation of the incomprehensible growth, we can suggest the influence of discontinuities in higher derivatives of the DMF caused by the use of splines to represent the *ab initio* data or rapid variations of the DMF in the complex plane (see **Discussion**). We performed a simplified calculation with use of the Born-Oppenheimer potential (without the spin-orbit coupling and other contributions) and an analytical DMF in the form of Ref. [12] with parameters from Ref. [23] (points), and the hump disappeared. We can conclude that, here as well, the splines are “to blame”. However, in a similar situation for phosphinidene (PH), all goes differently.

Fig. 7. The Einstein coefficients for transitions in state $X^2\Pi$ of thio(mercapto) radical from Ref. [23] (circles, $E'' = 368 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $v = 1-36$) and [22] (crosses, $E'' = 360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $v = 1-14$). The lower state: $J'' = 0.5$, $\Lambda'' = +1$, $\Sigma'' = -0.5$, $\Omega'' = +0.5$, parity e,+; the upper states: $J' = 0.5$, $\Lambda' = -1$, $\Sigma' = 0.5$, $\Omega' = -0.5$, parity f,-. The NIDL line is drawn through points $v = 2-6$, $\omega = 2711 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [24]. Point $v = 8$ is probably the anomaly. Points $v > 9$ are wrong. The vertical line shows the position of the minimum of the first excited electronic state. Black points, our calculation.

Fig. 8. The Einstein coefficients for transitions in state $X^3\Sigma^-$ of phosphinidene from Ref. [25] (circles) and our calculations: pluses, the Born-Oppenheimer potential and the analytical DMF from Ref. [25]; squares, the same with the modified potential (see text); crosses, the potential from Ref. [25] and our irregular DMF from Ref. [9] with 12 parameters fitted (i.e. adjusted by the least-squares method) to the analytical DMF from Ref. [25]; stars, the same but our DMF is fitted to the *ab initio* data of Ref. [25]; triangles, the overlap integral, I_{v_0} ; the lower line, the NIDL for the overlap integral; the upper line, the same one shifted up parallel to itself; $\omega = 2365.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [24]. The lower state: $E'' = 0$, $v'' = 0$, $J'' = 1$, $N'' = 0$, parity e,-. The upper states: $v' = 1-17$, $J' = 2$, $N' = 1$, parity e,+.

The phosphinidene data are shown in Fig. 8. The Einstein coefficients, A_{v_0} , from the database ExoMol (circles) plotted in the NIDL coordinates are «undulating». For comparison, we plotted the overlap integral, I_{v_0} , calculated by us, which demonstrates a nearly ideal NIDL. Here and below, we use only the Born-Oppenheimer potential ignoring the spin-orbit interaction and other contributions (the calculations depicted by pluses in Fig. 8 show that these simplifications keep the results nearly unaffected). According to the theory exposed in Appendix of Ref. [9], the transition amplitude can be represented as product of two factors, B_0T_0 , of which the second depends on the potential alone, moreover, only on its repulsive branch, and provides for the rapid decrease of intensity with the overtone number according to the NIDL, whereas the first one, which depends on both the potential and DMF, varies much more slowly, yet it can generate the “anomalies”, i.e. weak transitions when it crosses zero (“keen” beak-shaped anomaly at the semi-logarithmic scale) or approaches to zero without crossing the abscissa axis (“flat” anomaly). In fact, the overlap integral is nothing else as that same transition with $\text{DMF} \equiv 1$, therefore the NIDL must have the same slope (one and the same factor T_0) for any DMF having no non-physical singularities in the complex plane and slowly varying as compared to the wave functions of the vibrationally excited states. By shifting the NIDL line upwards parallel to itself, we see that the circles move in waves above this line. The reason for such a behavior could be the discontinuity of the higher derivatives of the potential at the equilibrium point, r_e , see Eq. (1) in Ref. [25] where the upper limit of summation, N , differs on the left and right of r_e . We did the calculation with a modified potential, in which $N = 1$ on both sides, and got the

same result shown by squares. Hence, the DMF is “to blame”, and we invoked our irregular DMF [9] with 12 parameters. First, it was fitted to the analytical DMF of Ref. [25] by selecting 200 points over the interval of 0-4 Å and adjusting the parameters by the least-squares method, the result is shown by crosses. The amplitude of the waves is decreased appreciably, yet the divergence with the NIDL remains still large. Then it was fit to 47 *ab initio* points from Ref. [25] over the interval of 0.7-6 Å and the waves disappeared completely (stars). The dip at high transitions is caused by the non-analytical potential-energy function.

Fig. 9. The DMF behavior of phosphinidene (PH) at the real axis (1: crosses, *ab initio* [25]; dotted line, the analytical DMF from Ref. [25]; dashed line, our irregular DMF [9] with 12 parameters) and in the complex plane along the line $\text{Im } r = 0.4 \text{ \AA}$ (2 and 3). 2 and 2' are real and imaginary parts of the DMF from Ref. [25]; 3 and 3' are the same for our irregular DMF.

The different behavior of the intensities is explained by Fig. 9, which shows how two DMFs vary at the real axis and in the complex plane along the line parallel to the real axis. At the real axis, these two functions are nearly indistinguishable and excellently reproduce the *ab initio* points in the interval of 1-2 Å where the dominant contribution to the original standard integral for the transition matrix element comes from. This plot in no way lets one to understand why they give such large discrepancies in intensities.

In the integral transformed (see **Discussion**), we shift the integration path into the complex plane where the dominant contribution is given by the region of 0.7-2 Å. Along the line parallel to the real axis, our irregular DMF behaves smoothly whereas the DMF from Ref. [25] shows unphysical oscillations and “curls” around it. The latter means a very fast change in the function (large first derivative) in the region of 0.7-2 Å embracing $r_e = 1.422179 \text{ \AA}$ [25], and this is reflected in the intensities of higher overtones. Remind that the NIDL is derived under condition that the DMF slowly varies as compared to the wave functions of the vibrationally excited states. As seen in Fig. 8, the problems with the intensities calculated with the DMF from Ref. [25] start at very low ν .

Nitrogen oxide, a special case

Fig. 10. The Einstein coefficients for nitric oxide, transitions $v'(=v), J', \Omega' \leftarrow v''(=0), J'', \Omega''$ in the ground state $X^2\Pi$ of nitric oxide from **Wong17** and **Hargreaves19** ($v=3-16$, circles) and **Qu21** ($v=3-26$, crosses). $\Omega' = J' = 1.5$, $\Omega'' = J'' = 0.5$, parity e,+; the SR branch. The NIDL line is drawn through points $v = 3-15$, $\omega = 1904.20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [24]. Points $v > 16$ are wrong.

Calculations for nitric oxide (NO) were performed in Refs. [26 (hereafter referred to as **Wong17**), 27, 28]. The potential energy, the spin-orbit interaction and the dipole moment in the ground electronic state as functions of r were calculated by quantum-chemistry methods in **Wong17**, and then the point-wise data were approximated by analytic and piecewise analytic functions. In particular, the DMF was represented by a rational function. Although the intensity calculations were performed for all possible Δv , the final line lists included only $\Delta v \leq 7$ in **Wong17** and $\Delta v \leq 16$ in [27].

Figure 10 shows the intensities of the R(0.5) line for the very weak SR rotational band with a change in the projection of the total angular momentum Ω ($3/2 \leftrightarrow 1/2$), and the picture looks similarly for the strong QQ and RR bands with no change in Ω ($1/2-1/2$ and $3/2-3/2$). The NIDL line slope, a , for the weak band is equal to 4.2, whereas $a = 4.1$ for the strong ones, with the standard deviation of the points from the line being 0.1 in both cases. Remind that the slope depends only on the steepness of the repulsive branch of the potential [3,8], therefore it must be the same for all bands, which, as we see, is fulfilled.

The transitions up to level $v = 16$ follow the NIDL well, but for higher transitions the calculations are obviously wrong. The situation is unusual in that the wrong points at $v > 16$ are below the NIDL as if there were no contribution from the repulsive branch of the potential, which must not occur (see the next section). In fact, the absolute value of the transition matrix element was restricted by the lower threshold of 10^{-9} D , which approximately corresponded to $v = 17$ according to Fig. 4 in **Wong17**, hence nonzero values at $v > 16$ should be ignored indeed. More interesting in the above-mentioned Fig. 4 is the behavior of the matrix elements at $v > 16$ that were calculated without

the threshold imposed: the intensity changes are wavy, and they will obviously go above the NIDL line in the respective coordinates. In our Fig. 10, a slight waviness is already visible in the interval of $v = 7-16$, and it is enhanced appreciably at $v > 16$ in Fig. 4 of **Wong17**. This can be related both to the poles of the analytic functions used to approximate the potential, spin-orbit interaction, and dipole moment, and to the discontinuity of the higher derivatives of the potential and spin-orbit interaction, since both the poles and the discontinuities are located near the region of classical motion.

To find out the reasons for the incorrect behavior of the intensities, we carried out an approximate calculation using only the Born-Oppenheimer potential (without other contributions) and DMF; at the same time, we eliminated the discontinuity of derivatives by setting the number of terms of the sum (see Eq. (2) in **Wong17**) equal to 3 on the left and right of r_e . For $v < 17$, our calculations “by eye” coincide with Fig. 4 of **Wong17**, but at $v > 17$ our intensities are 2-4 orders of magnitude lower (not shown). As in the case of phosphinidene (PH), the DMF strongly oscillates when shifted to the complex plane, which most likely explains the deviations from the NIDL. It should be noted that the incorrect shape of the functions cannot also leave intact the low- v transitions, thereby making it impossible to reach the high accuracy of calculations required to solve some modern problems.

Discussion

An essential feature of the overtone vibrational transitions is the extremely small value of the integral of the transition matrix element as compared to the integrand. We note that in such a case, the “exact” computer calculation of the integral must be treated with great care because the calculated value can differ from the true one significantly and moreover unpredictably. Indeed, the molecular functions are known only with some accuracy, but small errors in the integrand can lead to unpredictably large changes in the integral itself.

The problem in calculating this integral is that the entire domain of classical motion on the real axis contributes to it and that the integration path cannot be shifted into the complex plane, where the amplitude of the integrand could be reduced. Landau and Lifshitz [29] (see §51) transformed it to a different form and, shifting the integration path C into the complex plane, showed that the dominant contribution to the new integral came from a vicinity of the singular point r_0 , where the potential becomes infinite ($r_0 = 0$ in a diatomic molecule), i.e. not from the entire path C , but only from around r_0 , where the final result is formed; it was assumed that the potential and DMF have no other singularities that could affect the value of the integral and that the DMF was slowly changing as compared to the vibrational wave functions of highly excited states. The proof included

the aforementioned identical transformation of the integral, which made it possible to shift the integration path from the real axis into the complex plane and to apply the method of steepest descent. The goal was to reduce the integrand¹ to the value of the integral itself, which made it possible to use approximate expressions for the wave functions; in the original integral, as mentioned above, this was impossible because a small change in the integrand led to an unpredictably large change in the integral.

As a result, the transition matrix element was represented as a product of the so-called "tunneling factor", which describes the penetration of the system into the repulsion region, and a slowly varying function of vibrational quantum, v . In Ref. [9], we represented the latter as an integral over path C in the complex plane, in which the maximum value of the integrand on path C was of the same order as the entire integral. The tunneling factor is responsible for the small value of the transition matrix element and explains the exponential decrease in intensity with increasing transition energy [9], i.e., the NIDL (see below) and its relation to the repulsive branch of the potential. The term "tunneling factor" implies its interpretation as the amplitude of tunneling from the left turning point in the lower state towards r_0 followed by transition to the upper state at some point belonging to the neighborhood of r_0 and the "reverse tunneling" to the left turning point of the upper state. A similar phenomenon is known in the theory of collisions and nonradiative transitions under the name "dynamic tunneling" [30].

The potential and dipole moment of the molecule are formed due to the electrostatic interaction of charges, which is described by the Coulomb function $1/r$. As said above, the potential has the singular point $r_0 = 0$, where it tends to infinity due to the inter-nuclear repulsion, but also other singular points associated with the electronic contribution to the energy, namely the branch points [29] (see §79) at the intersections of the electronic terms at complex values of r ; the DMF also has branches at the same points [13]. We have shown that the pole of the potential at zero, or more precisely, the presence of the repulsive branch leads to the NIDL [3] and that the branch points do not distort the NIDL [13]. Thus, the analytical properties of the real molecular functions result in that the intensities of overtone transitions follow the NIDL, and, obviously, the corresponding model functions must also obey this rule.

The Coulomb function decreases not only on the real axis but also in any direction in the complex plane. Therefore, the model functions should not, at least, increase rapidly in the complex plane. Our calculations for CO show that moderate power-law increase in DMF (with power of 8 [9]) does not distort the NIDL. However, if the DMF oscillates or grows exponentially, as in Eq. (1), then the NIDL linear dependence is distorted, as shown in the figures. It is important to emphasize that we are talking about fast changes in the DMF specifically in the complex plane, where the main

¹ multiplied with the width of the integration region, which is on the order of 1 Å.

contribution to the transformed integral is formed, while there may not be fast changes on the real axis, as shown in Fig. 9 for PH. Rapid increase of the model functions prevents the path from shifting to the upper half-plane reducing the absolute value of the integrand to the value of the integral itself (see the beginning of this section). As a result, the value of the integral is no longer determined by point r_0 , but by another area, which leads to an increase in the calculation error.

Deviations from the NIDL are unacceptable because they amount to very strong, by times and orders of magnitude, changes in intensities (the scale unit in our graphs is 5 orders of magnitude!), which makes the calculation meaningless. We emphasize once again that the straight NIDL has a deep physical basis: it is associated with the repulsive branch of the molecular potential, whereas any deviations from the NIDL are caused by specific analytical properties of the DMF and the potential, which are properties of the given model rather than of the real molecule, and they vary greatly when the model changes. The general requirement is that it is necessary to consider only those models that give the straight NIDL, in which case the remaining relatively small discrepancies can be interpreted as calculation errors. To further refine the model, one can use the anomalies that are very sensitive to the choice of the functions [31].

Note that the above-mentioned deviations from the NIDL caused by nonphysical singularities of the potential and dipole moment should always lead to increasing intensities because in the presence of several singularities, the integral is determined by the one that gives the largest contribution [29]. From this point of view, the result for NO in Fig. 10 is noticeable because the intensities of high transitions are less than expected according to the NIDL. Such a behavior clearly indicates the presence of a technical error.

It is important to emphasize that the specific requirements for the model functions, such as the limited growth or the absence of oscillations in the complex plane, may not be met, unless this leads to distortion of the NIDL; nevertheless, in this case too, one can expect an increase in the calculation error, and not only for the high but also for the low overtones. In particular, the presence of nonphysical poles on the imaginary axis of the Meshkov *et al.* potential for CO [32], although it does not distort the NIDL, can introduce additional errors in the intensities of all lines, so that in the future it is desirable to construct a potential without such singularities. The use of the Šurkus variable in the model functions of the potential and dipole moment (see, for example, [22]) can also cause deviations from the NIDL due to the presence of poles in it.

Attention should also be paid to the fruitfulness of using several DMFs with significantly different analytical properties to compare the results of calculating the rotational intensity distributions in vibrational bands, as was demonstrated by us for the 7-0 band of the CO molecule [9, 13]. These can be functions that are completely regular in any finite part of the complex plane, for example, polynomials; functions with poles, such as Padé approximants and other rational functions;

functions with branch points. If it turns out that the distributions are very different [13], this indicates a defect in one of them or all functions. If, on the contrary, the distributions are very similar [9], then all functions are correct and the remaining differences can be interpreted as calculation errors.

Conclusions

The modern approach to the formation of the spectroscopic databases, such as HITRAN [33], HITEMP [15], ExoMol [14,34], etc. is to embrace all possible, including very weak, transitions. Special programs have been developed [35, 36] for calculating the frequencies and intensities of the vibrational-rotational transitions in diatomic molecules using model molecular functions, whose parameters are chosen on the basis of the experimental and theoretical data. Recently, more and more attention has been paid to the problem of improving the accuracy of calculations, which promises new applications [35]. However, this problem is considered only in terms of the accuracy of the numerical solution of the Schrödinger equation for given functions of the potential energy, dipole moment, etc., while the choice of the form of these functions often remains beyond the scope of these studies.

To obtain reliable predictions of the intensities of the overtone vibrational-rotational transitions, it is necessary to choose such model functions that provide for the straight NIDL (except for isolated anomalies) in a wide range of transitions up to the dissociation limit. In themselves, the very high transitions are of no practical interest due to the impossibility of observing them, but they serve as an indicator, a kind of "magnifying glass" that allows one to see defects in the model functions, which lead to a significant increase in the calculation error for all transitions including low overtones.

For improving the accuracy of calculations, it is also desirable that, in terms of their analytical properties, the model functions should be as close as possible to the real functions. In particular, the model potential may have a pole that creates the repulsive branch, and may also have branch points that imitate the intersection points of the electronic terms in the complex plane; at the same points, there should also be branchings of the dipole moment [13]. The popular generalized Morse functions using the Šurkus variable, strictly speaking, do not meet these criteria due to the presence of non-physical poles. The potential of Meshkov *et al.* for CO [32] has a physical pole at zero but its other poles have no physical meaning. We emphasize that the requirement formulated here regarding the analytic properties of the functions is not strict – only the requirement of the straight NIDL is strict. For instance, the Morse potential does not have a pole at zero, and yet the presence of the repulsive branch is already sufficient for the NIDL to be straight with the correct

choice of the DMF; the potential of Meshkov *et al.*, as mentioned above, has non-physical poles, which, however, do not spoil the NIDL.

Attention should also be paid to the behavior of the DMF when shifted to the complex plane: if the DMF oscillates, as we saw for PH and NO, this may be an obstacle to achieving the high accuracy required for some promising applications [35].

About the analytical properties, i.e. the presence of common branch points, the absence of non-physical poles in the potential and dipole moment, the correct asymptotic behavior at zero and at infinity, etc., we can say this: the closer they are to the properties of the real functions, the smaller the calculation error in both the high and low overtones. However, the practical implementation of this strategy requires a lot of work.

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Conflict of interests

The authors claim that they have no conflict of interests.

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